

IMI2 821520 - ConcePTION

ConcePTION

WP8 – Scientific coordination, project management & sustainability

D8.13 Landscape analysis and cost analysis

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Abstract

This deliverable serves as an interim report on the progress towards the final sustainability plan as crafted by work packages with the methodology and support from WP8. It outlines the steps that have been taken so far and provides an overview of the internal landscape of exploitable assets within the ConcePTION ecosystem, as well as the external landscape of successful IMI projects.

Departing from the landscape analysis that has been performed, the sustainability task force will now be able to support the further development of the assets identified by the technical WPs and use the insights from the external analysis to foster productive discussions with the WP team members for further progress with business model(s) generation. This will be done in close collaboration between WP8 (T8.7 team), WP6 (T6.5 team) and the communications team and in line with the division of responsibilities that were cooperatively defined. The T6.5 team offers their support in engaging key stakeholders; the communications team contributes towards an enhanced awareness; and the T8.7 team offers their business consulting support, thus jointly helping to inform sustainability. The three teams mutually support and generate insights for WP8 as well as for the scientific WPs, who are ultimately accountable for sustaining the value of their assets in the ConcePTION project.

In the months to follow, the group will be busy with further supporting WPs in defining the values of these assets, exploring the options of synergies and deliverable clustering, and moving forward towards a structured business model generation for the assets and the ecosystem as a whole. These efforts will then be elaborated on in the deliverables to come.

1. Introduction

The sustainability task force in WP8 aims to help other WPs identify the means of maintaining the value¹ that the ConcePTION project has to offer after March 2024 when IMI funding ends. The value of the project includes the knowledge bank, the milk biobank and medication related studies for maternal and child health. This deliverable aims to present our progress towards building a sustainable workstream within all work packages, by offering a report of the steps taken so far and a snapshot of the progress at the moment. It is crucial to note that all the information presented here is still work in progress, subject to change as a result of on-going discussions within the technical WPs.

Within this report, an overview of the landscape, both internal and external, will be presented to offer a more complete picture and a suitable starting point for further progress (Figure 1). For the internal landscape analysis, WPs within the ConcePTION project were mapped for those deliverables and assets that have the potential to be sustained and bring value to the ConcePTION learning health ecosystem. For the external landscape analysis, ttopstart's research triggered by the discussions within the ConcePTION core team was used, within which the finished IMI1 and IMI2 projects were studied for their sustainability, assessing the survival rate after the funding has ended, the earning models and governance structures, as well as the continued involvement of EFPIA partners. The outlook on the external landscape has been central for the ConcePTION project from early on, as indicated in the grant agreement, too.

¹ It is crucial to note that the mandate of the ConcePTION sustainability task force clearly states that the sustainability scenarios will not necessarily include the complete consortium, nor that all consortium members' needs and all project assets will be assessed.

Figure 1: Landscape analysis elements

Starting with the internal landscape analysis, a clear overview of the potentially valuable assets within the ConcePTION project is presented, offering a solid basis for any further assessments. WP leads were engaged in discussions and were given the opportunity to reflect on their work and its potential value. In parallel, it turned out to be very useful to use the research performed by ttopstart on the continuity of other IMI projects, so that lessons can be learned, and possible common denominators identified between the (un)successful IMI projects and the ConcePTION project, which could then be leveraged. The success stories also offer a great deal of inspiration and motivation for everyone involved, which is a key pre-requisite for such a complex and multi-stakeholder project as this IMI project is, ensuring that everyone remains properly engaged.

The landscape analysis has been a joined effort of WP8, overseeing the emphasis on sustainability and funding options, WP6, offering consultation on cross-stakeholder engagement and on extracting the value, the Communications team, contributing towards an enhanced awareness and the other scientific WP leads who provide the input on content, for which they are also accountable.

2. Methods

2.1. Internal landscape analysis

In this section, the methods used to perform the internal landscape analysis will be described.

2.1.1. Roadmap to sustainability building

Firstly, to kick-start our efforts and support in sustaining the project's outcomes, a roadmap was developed (Figure 2). Three parallel dimensions with 6 main tasks were identified to enable the sustainability building. Firstly, those assets that could be continued would be identified among the scientific WPs. Secondly, and rather in parallel, value propositions would be identified, and continuity needs for the previously identified assets would be laid down by the WP leads and with our support. Thirdly, potential operational scenarios and funding criteria would be explored. Lastly, the actual business plans would be formalized, all in collaboration with the respective WPs.

The team has put together a timeline for this roadmap. It is important to note that while there is a certain order to the steps laid down in the roadmap, some steps, for example, step 2, are iterative (see Figure 3). Moreover, the progress through these steps is iterative due to their inter-connectedness as well as the multi-stakeholder nature of the assets in the first place. Steps A, B and C in Figure 3 represent the iterations. In step A, value propositions and continuity needs are identified and subsequently stakeholders are engaged to provide feedback. In step B, in a close co-creative process with stakeholders, different operational scenarios are developed. In step C, the formalised and re-evaluated value propositions and continuity needs are incorporated within viable operational and funding scenarios.

At this point, and importantly for this deliverable, significant progress has been made with step 1 being completed and the initiation and significant progress of steps 2 and 3². Actions are now also slowly being taken towards step 4. Step 1 (and partially also steps 2 and 3) allow us to outline the landscape and their methodologies will therefore be elaborated on in the sections to follow.

Roadmap to Sustainability Building on WP6 Deliverables

3 parallel dimensions & 6 tasks

Figure 2: Roadmap to sustainability

Sequence of Engagement with Funders or Key Stakeholders

Figure 3: Timeline of the roadmap

2.1.2. Identifying assets and activities to be continued

Each scientific WP was approached so that those assets and activities that have the potential to be continued after the IMI funding is over could be identified. The WPs were offered either to partake in workshops organized by the task force to brainstorm together or to brainstorm internally and their input was subsequently reviewed by the sustainability task force. In either format, they were asked to brainstorm on the following questions:

What are the tools, products, methodologies & activities to be sustained?

² It is crucial to note that all the information presented here is still work in progress, subject to change as a result of on-going discussions within the technical WPs.

What are the key sustainability needs for activity/asset/deliverable? E.g. stable infrastructure, source of continuous funding, continuation of work itself, expertise, maintenance of tools, permanent staff, informatics infrastructure, technical infrastructure, etc.

Do you anticipate risks for sustaining past IMI Conception?

These discussions resulted in a list of deliverables that could be sustained and that will later be presented in the Results section.

2.1.3. Articulate the value to society & key stakeholders

Next in the roadmap, the value to society and key stakeholders was planned to be explored within the WPs, using the same setting of workshops and/or internal brainstorm sessions. As a first step, open-ended discussions were held within the WPs, prompted by the following questions:

What is the novelty each asset from WPX will bring?

- *What problem is the deliverable solving? What is the reason of doing the deliverable? what efficiencies is the solution providing? Why this solution and what are alternative solutions?*
- *Are there risks if deliverable is not continued?*
- *What tangible outputs from the project deliverable can demonstrate the value (are there timelines?)*
 - o *How does it add value for women (and infants)?*
 - o *How does it add value for society?*

Moreover, the value of the identified assets for each key stakeholder, i.e. patients, regulators, HTA & payers, academics & researchers, HCPs and policy makers was discussed, crucial for their future buy-in.

In order to formalize this crucial analysis of the deliverables further, more structured brainstorm sessions with WPs will follow in the upcoming months. As mentioned, this is a task that stretches across several months, due to its integral role in the business model generation. During the months to come, the value proposition of each asset to be sustained will be revisited within dedicated workshops across all the scientific WPs, with a representative from the sustainability task force present to guide the process. This will lay the basis for defining the value proposition(s), using the St. Gallen Navigator (Figure 4), as a first step towards a completed business model(s). The navigator focuses on the ‘who’, ‘what’, ‘how’, and ‘value’, offering an appropriate trigger for discussions. The in-depth-method for and the results from these discussions will further be elaborated on in the deliverables to come.

Figure 4: St. Gallen Business Model Navigator

2.1.4. Understand continuity needs

In a further step, WPs were invited to reflect on and articulate what it will take to continue IMI-ConcePTION assets by identifying the needed activities and resources for each asset.

What does it take to continue and operate identified assets. Please describe needed resources and activities.

- *E.g. infrastructure (governance structure) , technical infrastructure, staff, continuous source of funding, expertise, continuation of work, maintenance of tools (templates, protocols,), data access or other sourcing needs*

Does any of these assets require ethical advisory or legal counsel?

- *E.g. transparency needs, reporting*

Have you already identified challenges/risks for sustaining past ConcePTION?

2.1.5. Identifying levels of sustainability for each asset

Lastly, another level of assessment for this deliverable that was performed was gathering insights into the level of sustainability that each asset would require (Figure 5)

Figure 5: Levels of sustainability

The assets requiring Level 1 of sustainability need to be made available. Importantly, discussions on where the asset will be hosted and who will host them need to be held. The deliverables requiring Level 2 of sustainability need to create a sense of awareness with external stakeholders. It is important to realize who needs to be aware of them and what is the value they will bring to these stakeholders. Those activities requiring Level 3 of sustainability call for their adoption. Crucial to discuss is who will adopt or endorse them and how to make that happen. The deliverables requiring Level 4 of sustainability need to continue their activity. Appropriate funding sources and a roadmap toward this funding need to be identified for these highest level assets.

Such a classification of the previously identified assets provides us with valuable information on which exact team from this task force needs to be involved in further steps of exploiting the deliverables towards their highest potential. Level 2 calls for actions from the Communications team to cater for a strong marketing and external presentation. Level 3 requires the involvement of WP6 as these assets need to be matched with external stakeholders, whose needs are fulfilled with the asset at hand. Level 4 requires strong involvement of WP8, as funding opportunities need to be assessed and operationalized.

2.2. External landscape analysis

In this section, the methods used to perform the external landscape analysis will be described.

2.2.1. Filter process

First, it was crucial that the finished IMI 1 and IMI 2 projects were filtered out from the general database and then the projects that continued after their funding period were investigated in detail. Figure 6 displays the steps that were taken.

Figure 6: Filter process for external landscape analysis

2.2.2. Desk research into the ongoing projects

Next, desk research was performed into the continued projects using objectives defined in the ConcePTION project's core meeting. These are presented in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Objectives for the desk research of the external landscape

2.2.3. Follow-up questions with the continued projects' representatives

During the desk research, it became apparent that a further elaboration is required for the sake of completion, thus discussions with the continued projects' representatives were held. These were semi-structured interviews, using the following questions as the basis.

- Why did projects choose the route they did?
 - o What are common reasons for projects to pick an association?

- How does a project decide on the pricing level of the membership fees?
- What are the reasons for not involving EFPIA?
- What is the ideal country to set up the governance in?

3. Results

3.1. Internal landscape analysis

Using the above-mentioned method, the team was able to perform a landscape analysis at multiple levels.

3.1.1. Sustainability snapshot

As presented in Figure 8, upon approaching each technical WP, the first brainstorming sessions enabled the identification of the following deliverables that could be sustained per WP³. For each of the assets, a responsible person per WP was identified to be the liaison with the sustainability task force. A more detailed description of the identified assets, accompanied by the other levels of analyses will follow at the end of this subsection.

WP#	WP name	Deliverable to be sustained
WP1	Moving beyond pregnancy registries to enhance our understanding of disease-related pregnancy outcomes, medication use and safety of use during pregnancy	Methodology for pregnancy medication use and safety studies
WP2	Generate timely evidence about pregnancy outcomes, including perinatal and long-term effects following medication use during pregnancy	Adverse events app for optimized PV data collection and sharing
WP4	Establishment of a non-commercial, Europe-wide breast milk biobank and analytical centre	Breast milk collection network
WP5	Dissemination and education for HCPs, pregnant and breastfeeding women and general public	EU-wide knowledge bank and HCP trainings
WP7	Information and data governance, ethics, technology, data catalogue and quality support	Data catalogue to facilitate work in WP1 and WP2
WP8	Scientific coordination, project management & sustainability	Feasibility studies

Figure 8: Overview of the deliverables that could be sustained, per WP

3.1.2. Clustering and Prioritizing: ConcePTION as a learning health ecosystem

Although each work package generates discrete deliverables, the aim is to find sustainability solutions that will help maximize the collective value of ConcePTION as a learning health ecosystem, as originally envisioned at

³ For WP3, while their deliverables are crucial to the ConcePTION's ecosystem, they require Level 1 of sustainability, i.e. to merely be available, see section 3.1.5, hence no specific asset is identified moving forward towards sustainability. WP6 does not directly generate a deliverable that would be sustained. However, its stakeholder analyses are crucial backbones of assets of all the other WPs.

the beginning of the ConcePTION project. This begins by identifying “clusters” of deliverables with synergies and/or similar needs that would maximize their collective value to stakeholders and the society. Given the diversity of stakeholders, needs and operating models, it is important to identify clusters within ConcePTION rather than trying to find one solution that fits all. From a sustainability point of view this would not be possible; some funding scenarios may be in conflict with each other, and it is unlikely that a single funder would want or be able to fund all of ConcePTION. At the same time, the sustainability approach will consider ways to make it all work together.

Additionally, further filtering and prioritization of deliverables might have to be performed, so that the principle of quality over quantity is maintained and resources are used efficiently, allowing for a more realistic and focused business model generation⁴. The clustering and prioritizing are still in progress and are iteratively discussed within the sustainability task force and with the technical WP leads. It is important that the clusters do not lie in conflict to one another, and that maximum value is generated through the clustering. A more complete picture will be presented at a later stage.

3.1.3. Articulate the value to society & key stakeholders

As previously mentioned, this is the step of the roadmap that is the crucial starting point of business model generation, which also makes this task highly iterative and progresses over multiple months within the team’s timeline. Effort has been made into performing the first analyses into the value that the above-mentioned assets and the ecosystem itself provide. Identifying and confirming the value of the assets is an important pre-requisite for everything that follows, such as identifying the key users, value chains as well as revenue generation. The team has been devoting significant attention to this task, in consultations with the WP leads, feeding the outcomes into the first drafts of business models. However, for the sake of sticking with the mandate of the grant agreement, the business models and the value propositions therein will be presented in the deliverables to come. As previously mentioned, focused workshops will be held within each scientific WP in the following months, with a sustainability task force representative present, so that the value of each asset can be defined further.

3.1.4. Understand continuity needs

In parallel to exploring the value generated by the assets above, continuity needs and challenges of these were assessed. Below, some preliminary results of these needs are presented, however, these are still a work in

⁴ It is crucial to note that the mandate of the ConcePTION sustainability task force clearly states that the sustainability scenarios will not necessarily include the complete consortium, nor that all consortium members’ needs and all project assets will be assessed.

progress and the sustainability task force will continue to foster the discussions among the WPs in the upcoming months. The needs were assessed in three main categories, corresponding to the WPs actively

	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP7	WP8
Deliverable to be sustained	Methodology	Adverse events app		Breast milk collection network	EU-wide knowledge bank and HCP trainings	Data catalogue	Feasibility studies
Comms needs	Disseminate recommendations	TBD		Promoting the infrastructure Funding grants for academics	Developing value proposition Promotion of KB and HCP training	TBD	Promotion of study possibility
Engagement needs	Convince DAPs about the added value	TBD		Engagement with EMA and FDA for both endorsement and guidance Pharma for infrastructure use	Develop a user base community (HCPs & Women) Running a pilot	EMA and IMI to avoid competition	TBD
Sustainability needs	Source of continuous funding for network of expertise to expand and maintain state of the art methodology	Source of continuous funding		Source of continuous funding Informatics infrastructure Technical infrastructure	Source of continuous funding Governance and operating model	Product (structural) vs Activities (ethics)	Study Secretariat
Key Challenge	Lack of funding and lack of adoption by DAPs	TBD		Lack of funding Possible to work with industry? Lack of data analysis experts	Buy-in of funders Value proposition clarification Changing the culture	Catalogues need to be maintained and be interoperable How to make sure industry is not excluded?	TBD

Figure 9: Continuity needs

working on the sustainability of the ConcePTION project. These are the communications needs (key for the Communications team), the engagement needs (key for WP6) and the sustainability needs (key for WP8). The key challenge for each asset was identified as well, upon consulting the respective WP leads. For an overview of these, see Figure 9.

3.1.5. Identifying levels of sustainability for each asset

Lastly, as discussed, the team has identified the level of sustainability that each asset requires, similarly hinting at the further activities of each of the members involved. For an overview, see Figure 10.

	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP7	WP8
Deliverable(s) that could be sustained	Methodology	Adverse events app		Breast milk collection network	EU-wide knowledge bank and HCP trainings	Data catalogue	Feasibility studies
Sustainability type							
level 1: availability	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
level 2: awareness	X	X		X	X	X	X
level 3: adoption	X	X		X	X	X	X
level 4: ongoing activity	X	X		X	X	X	X

Figure 10: Levels of sustainability for each asset

3.1.6. Description of the individual assets with potential to be sustained

This section details the above-identified assets with potential to be sustained and narrates the results of the follow-up analyses of continuity needs and level of engagement. The sustainability task force has worked with the scientific WPs to identify the discrete aspects of these deliverables that could be sustained. These are summarized at the end of each WP subsection. Since the value of the ConcePTION project lies in the interconnectedness of different elements within the ecosystem, some of these pertain to multiple WPs. In the sub-sections under the table, more narrative descriptions of the scientific WPs and their deliverables are laid down. To emphasise again, there are no conclusions drawn yet from the above analyses, as they merely constitute the initial talks.

An undoubtedly important asset to be sustained is the state of the art methodology for pregnancy medication use and safety studies, which has been on the agenda of WP1 within the ConcePTION project. This methodology is based on secondary use of population healthcare data in five key areas, which are specific to disease areas and/or to different classes of medication. For newly approved medications, the utilisation pattern among women of childbearing age and pregnant women is important to inform feasibility of safety studies and safety measures but is usually unknown.

The outcome of this WP, i.e., an acceptable methodology in data source identification and data analysis, is crucial for the alignment across multiple stakeholders. This methodology would contain, for example and among others, an aligned definition of exposure by all stakeholders (T1.3/D1.5). Guidance documents will be created outlining standards for conducting medication safety studies in pregnancy using secondary data approaches based on the knowledge gained through demonstration projects and other WP1 tasks (T1.6/D1.8). The methodologies and network expertise will be determined by data sources and the sustainability solution will be focused on the data, not so much on the DAPs.

Sustaining of this asset will require sufficient dissemination of these recommendations, hence a solid involvement of the Communications team. At the same time, the DAPs' on-going involvement is crucial for obtaining data, therefore, continuous revisits and ensuring them of the added value will be key. DAPs from new geographical locations might have to be approached and properly engaged. For the asset's continued effectiveness, it will need to be regularly updated and scaled-up and will thus require a continuous source of funding. The funding is crucial so that the methodology can be scaled up to other medication classes, vaccines, and other diseases and also to increase the geographical coverage. A key impact of this asset is that the suitability of data sources to support pregnancy research through this methodology is improved, which can only be reached by the adoption of this methodology. Unless the developed methodology is adopted by the DAPs, the asset will not truly be sustained. For these reasons, this asset requires sustainability throughout all four levels.

The discrete aspects of deliverables to be sustained within this WP is:

- the state of the art methodology for pregnancy medication use and safety studies, based on secondary use of population healthcare data in five specific key (disease and/or class of medication) areas.

The current hypothesis of work for this WP is still to be determined.

WP2

 Adverse events app for
optimized PV data
collection and sharing

Optimizing PV data collection on reported pregnancies, sharing of data and analytical methodologies have been the main objectives of WP2. The adverse events app would enable for the deliverables resulting from these objectives to be operationalized. The app would offer a set of best practices on risk-benefit considerations and medication use in pregnancy both for HCPs and pregnant women. Several such systems are already in place, however, this then also comes with the threat of fragmentation, which WP2 tries to address by finding ways to analyse the data collectively. In collaboration with WP7, this app will be used receive information, possible from a variety of existing sources including smartphone applications (e.g. WEB-RADR), online electronic reporting via patient/HCP facing websites (e.g. Pregnant (LAREB), bumps (UKTIS) and electronic data feeds), etc. This will be a safe space where HCPs and women can report pregnancies. The system may then be used to collect, share and analyse (using automated data mining algorithms, database flagging / counting) enhanced pregnancy pharmacovigilance data. The design of the app allows women to continue providing updates on the longer-term health of the child beyond birth. This is crucial because we do not always know how medicines taken by the mother could affect the health and (neuro-)development of the baby later on. The app builds on the MedSafety app, developed in another IMI project, WEB-RADR, but is optimised for pregnancy. The app will be available for phones and tablets and is also designed to work offline. The app will be launched in English, mainly for the UK audience to first ensure it is functioning optimally. All information will be collected following GDPR regulations and will reside with MHRA, the Health Authority in UK.

Currently, discussions are held within WP2 to further discuss the deliverable in detail, continuing to assess the needs and challenges of its sustaining. So far, the source of funding has been identified as a major sustainability need. The app will require permanent staff for maintenance and an informatics and a technical infrastructure. In addition, it will be crucial that the guidelines for data collection receive continuous monitoring to ensure proper data management and quality. For this reason, this asset requires sustainability throughout all four levels.

The specific deliverables that allow for sustaining the results of this WP are:

- The data sources of exposures and outcomes in pregnant and breastfeeding women
- The data quality assessment tool
- Core data elements for primary source data
- Common data model for data sharing, pooled analysis and evaluation supporting further research into teratogenic effects risks during breastfeeding
- Signal detection tools
- ConcePTION app – to support provision of information and data collection in pharmacovigilance
- Extended pharmacovigilance (PRIM, ENTIS) as an alternative to pregnancy registries
- LIFETIME for long-term follow-up of outcomes of pregnancy exposures
- DECIPHer (TeratoPHEN) in support of human pharmacogenetic research

The current hypothesis of work is that the governance and operational model used for sustaining the deliverables of WP2 could also be leveraged for the sustainability of other deliverables.

WP4

 Breast milk collection
network

Unique to the ConcePTION project, this would be a central European self-sustaining network to assess the infant drug exposure through milk. The samples could be received at Uppsala Biobank, where they will be checked and registered in the biobank LIMS and stored in low-temperature freezers. If this turns out not to be the best option, other location alternatives will be explored. This deliverable comes with an accompanying set

of SOPs both for the milk sampling, storing, but also for assessing the drug concentration, etc. Standard documentation for pre-examination processes for breast milk handling and biobanking are developed as well.

A paradigm shift is called for with regards to utilizing the network, which requires a great deal of communication efforts. The use of the infrastructure needs to be promoted and the success from the demonstration studies needs to be presented to move from the stage of awareness to that of adoption. The role of regulatory authorities such as EMA and FDA is crucial for both endorsement and guidance. Advice will be sought from these bodies and recommendations will be made on utilizing the human breast milk biobank. Moreover, the engagement of pharmaceutical firms will be crucial for the infrastructure. As with the other assets, there is a need for continuous funding, to maintain appropriate tools, permanent staff and informatics and technical infrastructure. This asset acts on all four levels of sustainability, as it requires the on-going activity of continuous sample donations and the utilization of the infrastructure, without which the expertise would be lost.

The specific deliverables to sustain the results of this WP are:

- European Network to assess the infant drug exposure through milk
- Standard operating procedures
- System with a standardized information and format (public mega data information access)
- Bioanalytical facilities
- PK facilities
- Patient enrolment and/or sampling platform
- Governance committee and/or board

Our current hypothesis of work around the breast milk collection network is that BBMRI-ERIC would develop new capacity to use its existing biobanking infrastructure.

The knowledge bank would provide a “one stop shop” of information for women online and from HCPs. It aims to provide up-to-date evidence-based information to HCPs and members of the public on the use of medicines during pregnancy and breastfeeding. The content would be a collaborative effort of experts in the area of medicine use in pregnancy and breastfeeding. An SOP to guide the production and alignment of content for the EU Knowledge Bank has been developed and agreed by participating ENTIS members. ENTIS network would house and deploy the knowledge bank. The information in this database will be publicly available and will be in English. It will be in a form of a website and interfaces will be built so that national translations will be accessible and shareable with other apps and websites in respective countries.

At the same time, the HCPs would be trained about teratology and long-term outcome and methods of evidence generation in the ConcePTION project and how they can translate this in effective messages for women and their families. An accredited e-learning training programme would be developed. The focus will be on the basic principles of teratology, knowing where to find the right information and how to interpret it for a patient centred and evidence-based decision.

The knowledge bank and the trainings need to be properly promoted, which is where the communications team is required to step on. Moreover, the value proposition needs to become clearer and the use in practice needs to be discussed further. At the same time, a user base community should be developed and properly engaged as well as provide the proper endorsement to move the asset from the state of awareness to that of adoption. This is the asset that directly requires the adoption by mothers and HCPs and it would be very new to both of these groups. This requires a change in culture and the involvement of all the teams across. Even though ENTIS would be the potential host, its buy-in is required.

The specific deliverables to sustain the results of this WP are:

- ENTIS hosted one stop shop platform
- Accredited e-learning programme for HCPs

Our current hypothesis and approach towards supporting the sustainability of the EU-wide knowledge bank is that the ENTIS Network would house and deploy the new knowledge bank capacity provided it brings new revenue.

WP7

Data catalogue to facilitate work in WP1 and WP2

The WP provides ethical and governance support to other WPs, such as WP1 and WP2. This results in a set of best practices that can be sustained to enable the proper running of the above-described assets. For example, the rules by which DAPs will provide access to data are identified, proposals on ways of involving pregnant women in the learning health system are provided, governance frameworks for responsible re-use of data are defined, etc.

While the continuity needs are still in the process of being defined, it is important that EMA and IMI remain engaged and updated on the progress, to prevent possible sources of competition. It is crucial that a proper data pipeline is maintained and monitored for scalability. The catalogue needs to be update with new data sources that have the potential to enable pregnancy studies. At the same time, a negotiation tool should be established, allowing external researchers to engage with the researchers within the network. There also needs to be a certain guidance in place for the users so they know how to utilise these tools. These sustainability needs suggest the need for an on-going activity, implying the need of all four levels of sustainability. An important challenge is that there needs to be established a scenario in which the industry is not excluded from access to the data catalogue, which remains to be a point of discussion between the sustainability task force and WP7.

The specific deliverables to sustain the results of this WP is a data pipeline, which consist of:

- Catalogue, which needs to be maintained with data sources that have the potential to perform pregnancy safety studies)
- Negotiation tool, allowing external researchers to engage with researchers in the network
- Common data model
- Data quality framework
- Analytical functions for syntactic and sematic harmonization and key elements of pregnancy research e.g. pregnancy script to identify pregnancy cohorts
- Online community that is able to educate on how to utilise these tools (guidance) and enable cycles of continual optimisation

The current hypothesis of work for this WP is still to be determined.

WP8

Feasibility studies

The main asset to be sustained for WP8 is enabling the guidance of novel incoming projects. The sustainability of the ConcePTION ecosystem would benefit from a continuous stream of studies. Such studies however need to be (1) properly relatable to the ecosystem, (2) addressing key unmet needs, (3) professionally initiated and executed, and (4) as inclusive as possible. Also, for (candidate) study requestors, a clear and reliable entry point should be defined. This could be done through a ConcePTION Study Secretariat, which is our current hypothesis of work for sustaining the deliverables of this WP. Its purpose is to install and maintain a one-stop shop for study requestors and the QA and support measures to ensure smooth acquisition and running of projects. It is considered preferential to centrally coordinate incoming study requests because this aids in

(1) validating the need for such studies, (2) developing and refining the underlying processes, fee structures and business case, and (3) ensuring smooth transition to the to-be-established entity. Final responsibility over study design, results and conclusion will reside at the study coordinating center (not the Study Secretariat).

These studies could include population characterization studies, drug utilization studies, safety studies and/or feasibility studies and can be performed both under the DoA and outside of it. The study requestors are envisioned to be the EMA, EFPIA partners, biotech companies, but also other parties.

The process would begin with a submission of proposal, i.e. filling out a template and submitting. The study secretariat would then perform an initial fit assessment and a sanity check. The positive requests would then be discussed in the core team. A standardized request, including proposed timelines, will be developed and sent out to the DAPs, including a question on who would be interested to coordinate the study. Responses will be harmonized, discussed with the requestor and a selection will be made were needed. The requestor and coordinator develop and sign a contract for the feasibility study; the coordinator will contract the DAPs; the study secretariat will guide and support the process. To ensure inclusion of key knowledge in the process, 1 or 2 representatives from a standing committee will be included in the discussion. The feasibility assessment itself will be performed by the coordinator, with the secretariat monitoring the progress. The results will be discussed between the coordinator and requestor, leading to a go/no-go for the next steps. Then, a protocol will be developed between the coordinator and requestor, supported by the study secretariat, and standing committee. The study itself is then performed by the coordinator, with the secretariat monitoring it. In the end, a report will be developed by the coordinator and sent to the requestor.

A detailed set of responsibilities of the secretariat, as well as an initial budget draft are under progress and will be presented in the business models in the deliverable(s) to follow. It is key that the option to use the services of study secretariat is well promoted. The secretariat requires for an on-going activity, covering all four levels of sustainability.

To sum up, the specific deliverable to sustain the efforts of this WP would be the study secretariat and our current hypothesis of work is to build a network around it and define a clear governance structure to manage studies from request to delivery.

3.2. External landscape analysis

The filtering process as described in the methods allowed us to identify 13 IMI projects that were continued after their funding period ended. These were:

1. GetReal & GetReal Initiative
2. U-BIOPRED
3. SafeSciMET
4. PharmaTrain
5. EU2P
6. OpenPHACTS
7. OncoTrack
8. K4DD
9. ADVANCE

10. CANCER-ID

11. EUPATI

12. EFOEUPATI

13. PARADIGM

The detailed description resulting from the desk research and the interviews into each of these projects can be found in the Appendix.

The analysis showed that out of 167 IMI projects, the funding grant period of 96 has ended, and out of these, 13 continued after the funding period. These 96 projects have ended with an end date of August 2021 or earlier, which was when this study was performed. The 13 projects that have continued contribute to around 13.5% of the finished projects (Figure 11). Projects were considered continued if a legal entity representing the consortium was established and if an active funding model was identified.

Figure 11: The filtering process

Regarding the preferred funding models, the research showed that membership fees are the most popular funding model (Figure 12). Almost half of the continued entities were funded on membership fees. The pricing level of membership fees can vary per organization based on whether a member is from academia, industry or an SME. The projects using this funding model expressed the challenge in deciding on a pricing level for these membership fees at the start. Industry fees were in general higher, creating the main source of income, however, it also showed to be difficult to getting industry involved as well as enforce the payments. The second most popular funding models are mixed funding, which includes membership fees, grants, donations and testamentary provisions; and sponsorships. Third preferred funding were cash contributions and course fees.

Figure 12: Diagram of the funding model frequencies

It was found that the Netherlands or Belgium were among the easiest options to set up governance in, for the good support of their national platforms. Switzerland turned out to be very difficult admin-wise as it is not an EU member state, but the management there is rather easy. Italy, France and Germany showed to have quite high entry barriers, e.g. in Germany, high capital is needed and an organizational structure has to be firmly in place. Moreover, EFPIA partners were involved in 11 out of 13 projects.

The most popular mode entities include associations, followed by universities (Figure 13). Projects that are now a part of a university were mostly training programmes during the IMI project period.

Figure 13: Diagram of the legal entity frequencies

4. Discussion

Within this deliverable, the sustainability task force managed to show a rather exhaustive picture of the landscape, carving the first steps towards the subsequent business model generation and the following implementation. The deliverable attempts to provide a snapshot into what has been done within the sustainability task force and to lay ground for analyses and plans that will follow.

Observing the results of the internal landscape analysis, the assets that WPs identified as having the potential to be sustained are in line with the assets described in the mission of the ConcePTION sustainability task mandate. Namely, the valuable milk biobank, the knowledge bank and the medication related studies for maternal and child health are those assets that should be sustained to capture the value of the ConcePTION project. Importantly, the notion of a health ecosystem is apparent for the WP leads, notably realising the links that exist between the assets. While each asset will further be assessed for the value it brings for the key stakeholders, the key user for whom it is intended and the revenue potential, the links between these assets will be crucial to understand the synergies that make the ConcePTION project unique. This remains to be the focus of the sustainability task force and will further be elaborated on in the deliverables to come.

While the assets that were identified form a firm basis of the different levels of analyses that follow, the team keeps on collaborating closely with the WP leads to ensure that their ideas are being reflected properly⁵. Therefore, for the analyses and desk research that have followed, regarding the continuity needs, etc., nothing has been set in stone yet and is subject to further iterations and discussions. The analysis of the continuity needs showcases that the work of the communications team is crucial since proper dissemination and communication prove to be the overarching theme in the results. Similarly, within the engagement team, it

⁵ It is crucial to note that the mandate of the ConcePTION sustainability task force clearly states that the sustainability scenarios will not necessarily include the complete consortium, nor that all consortium members' needs and all project assets will be assessed.

remains important that the stakeholders continue to be engaged, whether this is the DAPs, the HCPs, mothers or the policy-making authorities. For some of the assets, the continued engagement with the pharmaceutical industry is crucial, which is why the findings of the external landscape analysis, EFPIA partners continue being involved in the IMI projects after the funding ends, are positive. The sustainability needs are similarly important, in most cases proving to be the key challenges for the assets, namely the need to secure continuous funding, calling for an on-going involvement of WP8.

Similar conclusions can be drawn from the levels of sustainability required, most identified assets require all four levels, underlining the importance of all sustainability task force members to be involved. At the moment, the team has already put together a set of hypotheses for each of the assets, with the plan to test and verify these in the months to come.

Analysing the external landscape has been crucial for the proceedings within the sustainability task force. Since valuable assets were identified internally and the group moves to develop business models for these while realising the synergies of the ecosystem, it is very useful to be able to see the funding and legal models that were employed in other IMI initiatives. The funding models identified in the external analysis will serve as a great inspiration for WP8 members of the task force that will be shaping the funding schemes in the years to come. The preferred membership fees funding model, but also the mixed funding might be the way to go for the milk biobank, but also the knowledge bank and the feasibility studies. At the same time, it is very useful to explore the option of associations, but also consider the option of further development within a university or a research entity, rather than establishing a brand new legal entity. This might be an option often forgotten, while possibly making more economic sense in a lot of scenarios.

Regarding any deviations from the DoA, this deliverable initially also called for a cost analysis, too. At the moment, there are already some outlooks into the options of revenue generation for the assets identified. However, for now the group has been focusing on completing the landscape analysis, as described in all the sections above. The costs and revenue analysis will be detailed in the later deliverables, integrated within structured business plans.

5. Conclusion

Owing to the landscape analysis performed, the sustainability task force will now be able to further develop the assets identified by the technical WPs and use the insights from the external analysis to foster productive discussions with the WP team members for further progress with business models generation.

For the months to follow, the group will be busy with further guiding the scientific WP leads in defining the values of their respective assets, exploring the options of synergies and deliverable clustering and then guiding the process of moving these forward towards a structured business model generation. At the same time, the hypotheses for the possible business scenarios will be approved by WP leads, refined, tested and validated. The core sustainability team will continue to meet and work on further refinements, fulfilling the role of consultants for the leads of the scientific WPs. These efforts will then be elaborated on in the deliverables to come.

Appendix

1. GetReal & GetReal Initiative

GetReal is about facilitating the adoption and implementation of RWE in health care decision-making in Europe. The GetReal project ended in 2017, after which the GetReal Initiative was established. The first GetReal project didn't focus much on sustainability which is why the GetReal Initiative was established. This project ended in April 2021 and now the GetReal Institute has been established, which builds on the success of the two IMI projects. The Institute is a platform, an incubator, a source and a hub. It is a member-led not-for-profit organisation, its legal entity is an association. The source of funding includes membership fees with a choice of an annual fee or a three-year plan with different prices depending on which organisation you are from. EFPIA such as Roche, Lilly, Boehringer Ingelheim, AstraZeneca, MSD and Janssen are involved.

2. U-BIOPRED

The U-BIOPRED project made a ground-breaking step forward in understanding asthma by uncovering several subtypes of severe asthma. When the funding period ended in 2015, the partners amended the consortium agreement to allow it to stay in effect as a governance model for handling IP and publications. Now it is the U-BIOPRED Alliance which is a project development membership community that is coordinated by BioSci Consulting. Its legal entity is unknown. Members of the community meet on a regular basis to carry out an ongoing dialogue to identify opportunities for new projects and to co-develop projects. The members consist of industry partners, academic partners, SME's and one disease foundation. The source of funding includes membership fees although the website does not state any prices of these. 7 EFPIA partners are part of the U-BIOPRED Alliance.

3. SafeSciMET

The SafeSciMET project aimed to establish a comprehensive education and training programme in safety sciences for medicines in Europe. The IMI project funding ended in 2016 and since 2017, the University of Konstanz is the leading partner of the SafeSciMET education programme under the responsibility of Prof Dr Daniel Dietrich. The organisation is a programme under a University. The source of funding is membership fees for the courses and the pricing depends on the type of company (company, SME, regulatory authority or academic institution). Partners include those from universities and from industry (Bayer, Roche and Sanofi).

4. PharmaTrain

standards and guidelines for the development of post-graduate diploma and master courses in medicines development and related fields. In 2014, the PharmaTrain Federation became the successor of the project which is now managing and further developing these valuable assets. PharmaTrain Federation is an accrediting and certifying not-for-profit organisation. Its legal term is an association. There are five different membership categories including course providers, companies, agencies and societies as well as individual members. The membership fees differ per category and vary between 150 per year and 1,000 per year. A lot of the partners from the PharmaTrain Project are still there to provide their support, both public and private institutions. EFPIA are still involved.

5. EU2P

EU2P aimed to improve the understanding of the risks and benefits of medicines in large groups of people worldwide. It is the European programme in Pharmacovigilance and Pharmacoepidemiology. The programme (legal term is university) consists of academic partners, associated partners and collaborative bodies such as an executive board, domain boards, examination and doctoral boards and the central office at the University of Bordeaux. Depending on the type of course offered, the fees differ. Short courses are the cheapest option followed by certificates and a Master's. EFPIA are still involved.

6. OpenPHACTS

The Open PHACTS Discovery Platform was developed to reduce barriers to drug discovery in industry, academia and for small businesses. All data can now be accessed through the integrated pharmacological data via the Open PHACTS API, Open PHACTS Explorer or apps. The Open PHACTS Foundation rises from the ashes of the IMI Open PHACTS project. With the completion of the IMI project phase, it was evident that the need was still very real and that the creation of what is now the sustainable output of the project, the Open PHACTS Foundation, a UK based not-for-profit membership association operating in an honest broker model with the aim of furthering access to linked, scientifically relevant data for disease research and medical intervention that will benefit the human race. The Foundation is registered as a company and a charity in the UK. EFPIA are still involved, members include both industry and academia (Eli Lilly & Company, University of Vienna, Maastricht University and UPF Barcelona) as well as a board of directors. It is unclear what type of funding model Open PHACTS Foundation has.

7. OncoTrack

OncoTrack identifies and characterises biological markers that help the understanding of the variable make-up of tumours and how this affects the way patients respond to treatment. Two spin-off companies were created as a result of the OncoTrack project to commercialise a technology used in the culture of organoids. These two spin-offs are Cellular Phenomics & Oncology Berlin-Buch GmbH. They were founded by Christian Regenbrecht and Reinhold Schafer of Charite Universitätsmedizin Berlin and Jens Hoffmann of the German biotech company Experimental Pharmacology & Oncology.

8. K4DD

The K4DD project brings together a range of world class scientists in Europe who jointly address issues that hinder the routine study of drug-target binding kinetics. The aim of the project is to enable the adoption of drug-target binding kinetics analysis in the drug discovery decision-making process. The project resulted in the creation of a spin-off company, Phenaris which will develop ToxPHACTS, a software that will combine K4DD and eTOX project outputs with the Open PHACTS discovery platform. Phenaris is a spin-off from the Pharmacoinformatics Research Group at the University of Vienna. Kinetics-db is a unique data repository for ligand binding kinetics. At the end of the 5-year period, the K4DD project released most of its data to the public domain. Phenaris built on their own contribution to the project and considerably enlarged the K4DD database and offered the largest data source for ligand binding kinetics accompanied with unprecedented analysis tools. The funding model is a pay per use.

9. ADVANCE

The ADVANCE project developed and tested new methods and data analysis tools to create a Europe-wide system that can generate solid evidence on how vaccines are faring once on the market. The legacy of ADVANCE is VAC4EU, an international non-profit collaboration platform that stands ready to act as a vaccine safety and monitoring system that helps stakeholders to make fast, informed decisions regarding vaccination strategies. VAC4EU enables robust and timely evidence-generation on the effects of vaccines in a collaborative manner in Europe for use by citizens, health care professionals, public health organisations and regulatory agencies. It is a multi-stakeholder international association with a study network to run studies and an open community for scientific debate. VAC4EU finances its activities based on membership fees, grants, donations and testamentary provisions and any transfer not prohibited by law. In addition, VAC4EU may charge VAC4EU services with cost covering fees and VAC4EU may also receive overhead for services to contract studies by the study network. EFPIA are not involved.

10. CANCER-ID

CANCER-ID aimed to develop new, less invasive ways of capturing cancer cells and genetic material from tumours from blood samples and analysing them for clues to what treatment is needed and how well drugs are working. The European Liquid Biopsy Society (ELBS) was established by the initiative of Prof. Klaus Pantel. ELBS is open to attract new partners and will be a hub for liquid biopsy research in European with the key goal to translate liquid biopsy assays into clinical practice for the benefit of patients. ELBS brings together people and institutions from all over Europe and beyond who would like to work on bringing the promising research results to the clinic for the future benefit of cancer patients. They are based at the University Medical Center Hamburg-Eppendorf. Funding is through means of donation – as a one time donation, as a standing order or as an estate. The EFPIA are still involved in the society.

11. EUPATI and 12. EFOEUPATI

The EUPATI project ran from 2012-2017 and the EFOEUPATI project ran from 2018-2020. The EFOEUPATI was launched to ensure the optimal exploitation and sustainability of EUPATI's core achievements. Today, EUPATI is established as an independent, non-profit Foundation in the Netherlands. It provides education and training to increase the capacity and capability of patients and patient representatives to understand and meaningfully contribute to medicines research and development and to improve the availability of medical information for patients and other stakeholders. EUPATI is co-financed by in-cash contribution from industry partners and in-kind contribution from public partners, as well as fee-based services to ensure continuous education and reliable information for patients, patient representatives and the wider public. The sustainability plan for EUPATI is based on a mixed business model with different interconnected funding streams serving to sustain the core EUPATI activities (The EUPATI Patient Expert Training Programme, the EUPATI toolbox and the EUPATI online portal) and enabling a widening of EUPATI's scope. Fee-for-service training/courses, in-kind contributions or direct financial contributions, grants offered by funding bodies, fundraising/crowdfunding (donations and reward-based crowdfunding). EFPIA are still involved.